
Antônio Barreto

Antônio Barreto is a farmer based at Casa Nova – Petrolina (Brazil). He is a leader of the local community, representing the populations that live in the Caatinga biome. He is also responsible for the community library, dedicated to the spreading of knowledge between the local population, mainly the young people.

PARTNERSHIP WITH THE UNIVERSITY: MANDAÇAIA CAMPEIRA AND ITS ACTORS

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Abstract

The Sao Francisco Valley and the Caating biome have significant importance for the global Brazilian fruit production and exportation. Mr. Antônio Barreto provided a clear and passionate feedback about the concerns of the fellow farmers he was representing. He expressed also their curiosity and request to receive more detailed information on the project results and, in particular, know further about the specific activities they participated in and interacted with BEESSNESS team members. As envisaged by the project coordinators and coordinators of partners Universidade Estadual do Oeste do Paraná, Universidade Positivo and

Universidade Federal do Recôncavo da Bahia, a one day workshop to be held with and for the local farmers and beekeepers was scheduled for November 27th, 2024. The aim is to interact and address the farmers concerns and questions, and provide recent information gathered about the area and its native bees. Namely levels of pesticides detected in the crop and natural areas assessed, type of flowers that foster health bee maintenance, bee populations that may be present and their most relevant displacement patterns. Potential strategies that could be use to protect local bee populations under the relevant crop yields required for exportation in a sustainable agriculture setting. The preparation of the workshop is already on course.